

INTERFACIAL ADHESION IN A CARBON FIBRE-POLYIMIDE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

A measurement of interfacial shear strength was carried out on a PAN-based high strain type carbon fibre-polyimide resin system. The interfacial shear strength obtained increased linearly with increasing rate of active surface area and also with increasing surface roughness of the fibre. When the carbon fibre with surface treatment was heated in hydrogen at 750°C, the active surface area rate didn't change, but the surface roughness increased markedly, and the return in the interfacial shear strength to that before the surface treatment was not perfectly. The regressive analysis was then performed on the interfacial shear strength using the factors of the rate of active surface area and the surface roughness. As a result, it was found that the interfacial adhesion strength depended almost upon the chemical bonding.

INTRODUCTION

The application of carbon fibre reinforced plastics in various field has grown substantially in recent years. Such a growth, however, is owing to progresses made in a number of areas which include improving the processing technology and the composite properties. Many of the composites properties depend predonimantly upon the adhesion property at the fibre-resin interface. Therefore, this adhesion property has been fairly extensively investigated to understand the nature of interface, in particular by correlating the surface properties of carbon fibre with the interfacial adhesion strength. However, there still remains considerable mysterious facts, including the adhesion behaviours contradicting with each other, about the nature of the interface, even on epoxy resin matrix

composites which show the greatest broadening in application. Some of them seem to be ascribed to the use of different techniques for characterizing the carbon fibre surface and the interfacial adhesion, which are titration of acidic group [1-3], analysis of the peaks in the ESCA spectrum [4-6], measurement of graphitic layer plane diameter [7] and active surface area [8,9], and measurement of interlaminar shear strength [1-3,5] and interfacial shear strength [4,6,9], respectively.

It is, to the contrary, thought useful that the nature of interface is investigated on different composites in which different resins are used as the matrices, even at the present stage being insufficient in understanding the nature of interface between carbon fibre and epoxy resin.

In this paper, the adhesion property was then investigated on a carbon fibre-polyimide resin system. Although polyimide resin matrix composites have higher use temperatures compared with those of epoxy resin matrix composites, and the application field in which such a thermostability can be utilized is expected to expand, there is little investigation on the interfacial adhesion property of the composite.

The purpose of this paper is to correlate the surface properties of carbon fibre to the adhesion strength at the interface between carbon fibre and polyimide resin, which is measured by using a single filament-axially embedded, dogbone-shaped specimen, and to describe the effect of reducing a surface-treated carbon fibre by heat-treatment in hydrogen gas on the adhesion strength.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Four PAN-based carbon fibres were used. They were Torayca X550-U and X550-S, and Besfight STIII-U and STIII-S, supplied without sizing treatment by the manufacturers, U and S signify respectively carbon fibres without any surface treatment and with a surface treatment for improving adhesion to epoxy matrices. The hydrogen treatment for the carbon fibres with surface treatment was performed by heating the fibres in a flow of hydrogen gas at 750°C for 60 min.

A polyaminobismaleimide (Kerimide 601) and N-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidene were used as polyimide resin matrix and the solvent, respectively.

Characterization of Carbon Fibre Surface

As specific surface area, rate of active surface area, and surface roughness of the carbon fibres, the values which have been described elsewhere [8], but those of the hydrogen treated fibre were measured in this investigation by the same methods, processes of which were as follows:

In the measurement of the specific surface area, the carbon fibre was first heated at 100°C in vacuum, and then a krypton adsorption isotherm was obtained. After that, the carbon fibre was degassed again in vacuum up to 950°C, and then a krypton adsorption isotherm was obtained. The specific area was calculated from these data by the BET method.

After the krypton adsorption measurement, the carbon fibre was degassed again in vacuum at 950°C, and then oxygen gas at a low pressure was admitted to bring into contact with the fibre at 300°C. The specific active surface area was estimated from the amount of chemisorbed oxygen on the carbon fibre being based on an assumption that all of the chemisorbed oxygen atoms formed carbonyl groups with the protrudent peripheral carbon atoms of graphitic basal planes in the carbon fibre surface. The ratio of specific active surface area to specific surface area for the fibre degassed at 950°C was calculated as the rate of active surface area.

An evaluation of the surface roughness was carried out as follows: The optical diameter of the fibre was first measured from the Fraunhofer diffraction pattern of a He-Ne laser beam. From the mean optical diameter, the surface area per unit length of a single filament, SA_L , was calculated, being based on the assumption that the filament was a column having the circular or elliptical crosssection with the diameter obtained. Next, another surface area per unit length of the filament, SA_{100} , was calculated from the specific surface area at a degassing temperature of 100°C, weight per unit length of a yarn and filament number in a yarn. Surface roughness, Roughness, was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Roughness} = (SA_{100} - SA_L) / SA_L.$$

ESCA spectra were measured on the carbon fibre surface. Surface oxygen concentrations were estimated from the areas of peaks attributed to C_{1s} and O_{1s}, correcting for the elemental sensitivities.

Measurement of Interfacial Shear Strength

A single filament-axially embedded, dogbone-shaped specimen was prepared, using a silicone mold, after Drzal's technique [4,9]. The mold had a cavity with 30 mm long, 2 mm wide and 3 mm deep gauge section. The single filaments used were laid in a depth of 1 mm from the bottom of the mold cavity, and then a resin solution heated at 80°C was poured into the cavity of the mold heated at 80°C. The mold with solution was maintained at 80°C for 16 hours to evaporate the solvent. The specimen in the mold was cured by heating at 120°C for 3 hours and at 150°C for 3 hours, in sequence. The specimen was removed from the mold, and then cured at 180°C for 2 hours. The top and bottom surfaces of the cured dogbone specimen were shaved and polished to a specimen thickness of 1 mm with silicon carbide papers and diamond pastes, to improve the transparency. After that the specimen was post-cured at 180°C for 16 hours. The specimen was stored in a temperature- and humidity-conditioned room till the measurement.

The specimen was stressed until the number of fragments of the filament fractured in resin was saturated under a transmitted light microscope with polarized light illumination in the air-conditioned room, and the length of fragments was measured. The critical transfer length, l_c , is given by

$$l_c = 4\bar{l}/3,$$

where \bar{l} is the mean fragment length [10]. The interfacial shear strength, τ , is calculated according to the equation:

$$\tau = (\sigma_f/2)(d/l_c)$$

where σ_f is the fibre tensile strength at a gauge length of l_c , the critical transfer length, and d is the fibre diameter. The tensile strength, σ_f , at gauge length of l_c was estimated from the single filament strengths at gauge lengths of 5, 10, 20 and 40 mm, applying Weibull statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the outer surface of a PAN-based carbon fibre, graphitic layer planes can be regarded to be oriented parallel or nearly parallel to the fibre surface, though the size of the graphitic layer planes are small in a carbonized fibre compared with those in a graphitized fibre.

On the surface of such a fibre, inner carbon atoms of the graphitic layer planes are chemically inert, but the protrudent carbon atoms on the peripheries of the graphitic planes are chemically active and are combined with functional groups many of which contain oxygen atoms. In a carbon fibre-epoxy resin system, the carbon fibre surface is thought to be bound with resin molecules chemically through these functional groups [1-6]. The specific active surface area or the rate of active surface area obtained from the oxygen chemisorption is considered to be a measure of the amount of the peripheral protrudent carbon atoms, being active chemically. In fact, it has been observed in several papers that an interlaminar shear strength or interfacial shear strength of a carbon fibre-epoxy resin system depends upon the concentration of functional groups [1-3], or of oxygen measured by ESCA [4-6], or the length of the periphery of graphitic layer planes [7], and the above mentioned thought has been supported. In addition, we have found that the concentration of surface oxygen determined by ESCA increased linearly with the rise of active surface area rate of the same type of fibre, and the interfacial shear strength depends more clearly upon the rate of active surface area of the carbon fibre in the carbon fibre-epoxy resin system [9].

The interfacial shear strengths obtained in the present study are then plotted against the active surface area rate in Fig. 1. An

Figure 1. Interfacial shear strength as a function of active surface area rate for PAN-based carbon fibres.

excellent linear relationship is seen between them. This result may be interpreted to be an evidence that the interfacial adhesion between the high strain type of PAN-based carbon fibre and the polyimide resin is due to the chemical bonding alone.

However, there may be the contribution of the mechanical bonding to the interfacial adhesion, because of the rough surface of the carbon fibres. As regards the surface roughness, on the surface of PAN-based carbon fibres many wrinkles or ridges run nearly along the fibre axis, which are not perfectly parallel to each other and occasionally branch or coalesce. In addition, the fibre surface is considered to have microundulations, in particular at a surface-treated fibre.

The interfacial shear strength was then plotted against Roughness in Fig. 2. There is also seen a very good linear relationship between both the factors. It can be said that this is a consequential result, because Roughness increases linearly with increasing active surface area rate as has been already shown in a previous paper [9]. This linear relationship between Roughness and the active surface area rate can be understood from the definition of Roughness; This relationship implies that while the surface area of the carbon fibres increases by the surface treatment, the active surface area or the amount of active carbon atoms of the surface increases.

Figure 2. Interfacial shear strength plotted against surface roughness for PAN-based carbon fibres.

At all events, the above mentioned results suggest the following three possibilities in the interfacial bonding to contribute to the adhesion: The first is the contribution of the chemical bonding alone, the second is that of the mechanical bonding, anchoring, alone, and the third is that of both.

In order to find which of the bonding contributes to the interfacial adhesion, the effect of eliminating the reactivity of the surface functional groups on the interfacial shear strength was investigated using one of the surface treated fibres, Torayca X550-S. The elimination of reactivity was made by heating the fibre in hydrogen gas at 750°C for 60 min. The results obtained are shown in Table 1. The oxygen concentration, by ESCA, in the fibre heated in hydrogen gas decreases to that of the untreated fibre. Nevertheless, the active surface area rate does not change from that of the surface treated fibre. Moreover, the surface roughness expressed with Roughness increases markedly. And the interfacial shear strength decreases from that of the surface treated fibre, but it is higher than that of the fibre without surface treatment. The following is considered from these facts: A fairly large amount of the functional groups combined with the peripheral active carbon atoms of the graphitic basal planes in the surface treated fibre are replaced by hydrogen atoms. The contamination brought about in the carbonization and/or surface treatment processes should be cleaned up by heating the carbon fibre in hydrogen gas, and the specific surface area and as a

TABLE 1
Effects of surface treatment and heat treatment in hydrogen on interfacial shear strength and surface properties of a PAN-based carbon fibre, Torayca X550.

Fibre	Interfacial shear strength (MPa)	Oxygen concentration by ESCA (%)	Rate of active surface area (%)	Roughness (%)
untreated	20.3	8.5	7.7	21.0
surface treated	41.7	14.5	13.4	35.8
hydrogen treated	26.7	8.4	13.3	90.8

result Roughness should increase, because the fibre was heated at a high temperature of 750°C. However, this value of Roughness is larger than one can expect from that of the fibre degassed at 950°C [8].

If the interfacial adhesion depends on the mechanical anchoring alone, the interfacial shear strength with the hydrogen-treated carbon fibre should be higher than that of the surface treated fibre without hydrogen treatment. Accordingly, the possibility of the contribution of only mechanical anchoring is almost deniable, but some extent of the contribution is undeniable.

Furthermore, the contribution of the physical bonding, van der Waals forces, to the interfacial adhesion can be regarded as negligible. The interfacial shear strength values were treated by the regressive analysis, using the least-square method, on the basis of the assumption that the interfacial adhesion is formed by both of the chemical and mechanical bondings. The following equation was obtained:

$$\tau = 375.1A + 8.782R - 10.319$$

where A is the active surface area rate, and R is the surface roughness, Roughness. The interfacial shear strengths measured coincide well with the regression estimates obtained by the equation, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Interfacial shear strength measured versus regression estimated for PAN-based carbon fibre-polyimide resin system.

The increment in interfacial shear strength by roughening the fibre surface with the surface treatment were calculated to be 5.7 and 4.1%, respectively, for both the fibres, X550 and STIII, from this equation. This indicates that the increment in the interfacial shear strength by the manufacturer's surface treatment is due almost to the increasing chemical surface activity of the fibre.

From the results mentioned above, it can be conclusively said that in the PAN-based high strain type carbon fibre-polyimide resin system the strength of interfacial adhesion is due almost to the rate of active surface area of the fibre.

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